

Impact of Competitiveness in Market Orientation on Business Performance in Vietnamese Cashew Enterprises

Vo Thi Thuy Duong

Ho Chi Minh City University of Economics and Finance (UEF), Ho Chi Minh City, 84, Vietnam

<https://orcid.org/0009-0005-7233-8072>

***Dao Le Kieu Oanh**

Ho Chi Minh University of Banking (HUB), Ho Chi Minh City, 84, Vietnam

* Corresponding Author: oanhdlk@buh.edu.vn; <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4858-9099>

Abstract

Background: In an increasingly competitive global landscape, businesses are prioritising market-oriented competitiveness as a strategic foundation to enhance performance. However, the specific mechanisms through which market orientation translates into tangible business results require further empirical clarification, particularly within emerging markets.

Objective: This study evaluates the impact of market orientation competitiveness on business performance by examining the mediating roles of market forecasting ability, adaptability to change, market creation ability, and competitive advantage.

Methodology: The research utilised survey data from 503 respondents representing 260 cashew enterprises in Vietnam. The reliability of the measurement scales was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha and Exploratory Factor Analysis (EFA) via SPSS. The structural model and hypotheses were tested using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS software.

Results: The findings demonstrate a significant positive impact—both direct and indirect—of market orientation competitiveness on business performance. The intermediary variables, particularly competitive advantage and market adaptability, serve as critical pathways for enhancing organisational outcomes.

Unique Contribution: This study provides a robust empirical foundation for Vietnamese cashew enterprises to consolidate their market orientation. It offers policymakers deeper insights into the industry's strategic needs, facilitating the development of targeted support frameworks and development directions for the sector.

Conclusion: Market Orientation Competitiveness is a primary driver of Business Performance in the cashew industry, enabling firms to navigate market volatility and sustain growth.

Key Recommendation: Enterprises should prioritise investments in market intelligence and adaptive capabilities to bolster their market orientation competitiveness, thereby achieving superior and sustainable business performance.

Keywords: business performance, competitiveness, competitive advantage, market orientation, Vietnamese cashew industry.

Introduction

In the context of an increasingly complex global economy, digital transformation, and deep economic integration, market orientation competitiveness (MOC) has become a strategic pillar helping businesses maintain competitiveness and adapt flexibly to customer demands. Modern research indicates that MOC not only assists businesses in better understanding and meeting customer needs but is also closely related to other organisational outcomes such as business sustainability and brand reputation (Hanaysha & Al-Shaikh, 2024). Several studies also show that when businesses adopt effective market-oriented strategies, they tend to enhance innovation and thus improve their competitive advantage (CA) in the market (Irfandi et al., 2025).

According to statistics from the Vietnam Cashew Association (Vinacas), the total export value of Vietnamese cashew kernels reached US\$4.6 billion. Exports to European countries were the highest, exceeding US\$996 million, followed by the US market at over US\$934 million, the Middle East at US\$678 million, and China at US\$667 million... To achieve this revenue, the total export volume of cashew kernels exceeded 700,000 tons. Based on the ratio of raw to kernel production at Vietnamese cashew enterprises, in order to produce this amount of kernels would require 3 -3.5 million tons of raw cashews. However, according to data from the General Statistics Office, Vietnam's annual raw cashew production only reaches around 350,000 to 370,000 tons. Therefore, Vietnam still needs to import a large amount of raw cashews from African markets, Cambodia, Indonesia,... to serve production. Both raw materials and finished cashews require international trade with other markets, posing difficulties for Vietnam in terms of contact, monitoring, management, and transportation to ensure the most efficient buying, selling, and delivery of goods. Market fluctuations, climate change, the impact of war, and cultural differences require Vietnamese businesses to constantly grasp potential changes in order to respond promptly and develop appropriate strategies. Identifying MOC helps businesses better understand customers, competitors, and market reactions, thereby ensuring business efficiency. This is a pressing need for businesses in general, and especially for businesses in particular, in the face of fierce competition and threats from all sides.

Luo et al., (2025) in a recent study showed that MOC helps enterprises to predict the market, thereby creating business efficiency. (Morgan et al., 2009) said that MOC creates CA, which is the premise leading to the success of enterprises. So what are the factors that evaluate the MOC of enterprises? How should it be evaluated? Does the path from MOC to business efficiency go through any intermediate factors or create a direct impact? What criteria are used to determine the most optimal business performance (BP) when some studies suggest that BP should be measured through financial indicators such as ROA, ROE, ROS... (Ahmad & Pi-Shen, 2009), while other studies suggest that BP should be measured through non-financial

indicators such as satisfaction of business owners with the company's development, satisfaction of customers and employees with the company, good relationships with suppliers, a cohesive working environment, products and services accepted in the market and image building (Kaplan & Norton, 1996).

This study is a combination of two models of Luo et al (2025) and Morgan et al (2009) plus some other factors to study the impact of MOC on BP through the intermediaries Market forecasting ability (MFA), Changing Adaptability (CAD), Market creation ability (MCA), Competitive advantage (CA) and also measure the impact between intermediary factors, thereby clearly assessing the direct and indirect impact from MOC on BP. This study also inherits from (Kaplan and Norton, 1996) including both financial and non-financial indicators in measuring BP to have a more comprehensive view.

The next presentation is organised through the steps of summarising previous studies in part 2, then presenting the methodology, research model building process, data collection in part 3, research results achieved in part 4, drawing conclusions and managerial implications, limitations, and future research directions in part 5.

Literature review

According to Morgan et al, (2009), MOC is the ability of enterprises to collect and effectively use market information, share internally, and respond quickly to create higher value for customers than competitors, thereby improving competitive position and business results. The main components of MOC include: (1) Customer orientation: the ability to understand current and future customer needs to create superior value, (2) Competitor orientation: the ability to analyze, forecast, and respond strategically to competitors' moves, (3) Cross-functional coordination: the ability to share information and coordinate effectively between departments to respond to the market, (4) Adaptability and responsiveness: the ability to implement actions based on market information in a timely and flexible manner.

Martin et al., (2009) pointed out that MOC is an important source of sustainable CA and is a complete model for leaders in clarifying the mechanism of conversion from awareness to action Lambin and Schuiling, (2012) is more comprehensive in stating that MO is a common business culture in organizations through functional coordination, profit-increasing goals and pricing solutions. The synthesis of the two models of Morgan et al (2009) and Luo et al (2025) as well as a deeper assessment of the influence of other intermediary factors on BP or the impact between intermediary factors helps researchers and planners to see a more comprehensive picture of the path from MOC to BP.

Methodology

Research model

MOC is considered a fundamental capability that helps form dynamic capabilities, in which the ability to predict the market is a form of dynamic capability that allows enterprises to recognize early, learn and adapt to environmental fluctuations (Day, 2011). Through empirical research on 800 enterprises, Luo et al (2025) built a market forecasting framework using multi-source data and time series analysis techniques to determine that the stronger the forecasting capability, the more accurate the strategic decisions of the enterprise, thereby increasing business efficiency. Inheriting from these studies, hypothesis H1 was formed:

H1: Market orientation competitiveness creates Market Forecasting Ability

MOC promotes learning from customers, competitors and the environment, learning capacity facilitates continuous improvement, helps businesses detect opportunities, restructure resources, adapt quickly to changes, including organizing, planning, directing, helping people respond effectively to change and instability, thereby improving business results (Baker & Sinkula, 1999). Hypothesis H2 is established as follows:

H2: Market orientation competitiveness creates Changing Adaptability

Jaworski et al., (2000) has a different view when arguing that instead of just adapting to the available market, enterprises creating new markets or reshaping the current market structure will create initiative, easier to develop and expand. Market shaping capacity is the ability of a company to create, form and adjust the market (Wenzel, 2021). Combining the consensus from these opinions, hypothesis H3 is included in the model:

H3: Market orientation competitiveness creates Market Creating Ability

Morgan et al (2009) argues that MO is the culture and behavior of an organization that aims to create, disseminate and respond to market information, forming marketing capacity through the ability to deploy and coordinate resources such as market research, positioning, branding, distribution, communication, price... to meet customer needs. These factors help businesses create differentiated value, create CA, thereby achieving desired business results. Inheriting from this model, hypothesis H4 is integrated into the research model as follows:

H4: Market orientation competitiveness creates Competitive Advantage

The ability to predict the market helps businesses rely on information from customers, competitors, and changes in the surrounding environment to make judgments and evaluate market trends, thereby promptly making adjustments and restructuring to respond and adapt better to new conditions. According to dynamic capability theory, Day (2011) argue that early identification of market fluctuations helps businesses proactively adjust and restructure resources to adapt to change. Based on this, market forecasting not only provides information about the future but also triggers structural adjustment decisions within the organization, thereby enhancing adaptability. Hypothesis H5 is included in the research model to better evaluate the relationship between MFA and CA:

H5: Market Forecasting Ability creates Changing Adaptability

CAD helps businesses recognize, react, and quickly adjust strategies, structures, and processes to adapt to changes in the external environment. The MCA helps businesses create, reshape, or transform market structures, and adjust the behavior of market actors through proactive actions of businesses (Nenonen & Storbacka, 2021). Businesses that want to shape the market must first have high adaptability such as understanding trends, responding flexibly, and shifting from reacting to proactively shaping. Therefore, hypothesis H6 is established:

H6: Changing Adaptability creates Market Creating Ability

When enterprises can create markets, they will be more proactive in all aspects from pricing, responding to changes, redefining market boundaries, changing the rules of the game, changing the structure and operating mechanism of the market, leading to sustainable CA by creating strategic differentiation, determining the initiative and being difficult to copy by competitors (Nenonen & Storbacka, 2021). Hypothesis H7 is built:

H7: Market Creating Ability creates Competitive Advantage

Synthesizing from the interpretation of the above hypotheses, with the common goal from the studies all aiming at the final destination of business performance, hypotheses H8, H9, H10, H11 are formed as follows:

H8: Market Forecasting Ability impacts Business Performance

H9: Market Adaptability impacts to Business Performance

H10: Market Creating Ability impacts to Business Performance

H11: Competitive Advantage impacts to Business Performance

So does MOC directly impact business results? Or must it go through intermediate factors? Narver and Slater (1990) argued that MO is positively related to business profits, Jaworski et al (2000) also argued that organizations with MOC, dissemination and response to market information related to current and future needs of customers are likely to achieve superior performance. The hypothesis that MOC directly impacts business results is also included in the research model for a clearer assessment from all angles:

H12: Market Orientation Competitiveness impacts directly to Business Performance

Based on the above theoretical foundations, inheriting and synthesizing from previous models, developing from two original models of Luo et al (2025) when pointing out that the MOC helps enterprises to predict the market, thereby creating business efficiency and the model of Morgan et al (2009) stating that the MOC creates CA, thereby leading to the success of enterprises, so the research model to evaluate and measure the impact of MOC on BP through the intermediary of MFA, CAD, MCA, CA is built as follows:

Figure 1: Proposed research model

Research Method

Data collection methods

Survey questionnaires were sent to 260 businesses, each business receiving two questionnaires, for a total of 520 questionnaires designed on Google Forms and sent to businesses via email or social network. After two months of research, 512 responses were collected. After cleaning and removing unqualified questionnaires, 503 responses remained (96.7% of the total number distributed). Of these, 246 (48.9%) were business leaders and 257 (51.1%) were departmental

managers. The majority (71.6%) of businesses were over 5 years old and had more than 20 employees (73.0%).

Research Methods

After collection, the data were synthesized and processed through the following steps: (1) reliability assessment through Cronbach's Alpha; (2) exploratory factor analysis EFA using SPSS software; (3) confirmatory factor analysis CFA; (4) running the SEM linear structure model using PLS-SEM software. All analyses were performed using SPSS 25 and PLS-SEM following a strict process, ensuring reliability and generalisation of results; choosing PLS-SEM is suitable for complex models and allows simultaneous testing of causal relationships when measuring the impact of MOC on BP at Vietnamese cashew enterprises.

Research results

Testing the reliability and validity of the scale

The reliability and validity of the scales in the model are assessed through indicators such as: Cronbach's Alpha coefficient; Composite reliability (CR), convergent validity (AVE), discrimination according to Fornell-Larcker index and heterotrait-monotrait index (HTMT), in addition, the index measuring the quality of observed variables (Outer loading) is also used. The conditions for the scale to ensure reliability and validity are: CR and Cronbach's coefficient > 0.7 , AVE > 0.5 , Fornell-Larcker $< \sqrt{AVE}$, HTMT < 0.85 and Outer loading < 0.708 (Hair et al., 2013).

Table 1: Reliability and convergence of measuring scales

Measuring scales	Cronbach's alpha	CR	AVE
MOC	0.897	0.923	0.706
MFA	0.820	0.893	0.735
CAD	0.892	0.933	0.822
MCA	0.887	0.930	0.816
CA	0.825	0.896	0.742
BP	0.910	0.933	0.737

(Source: author's analysis)

All variables in the model are measured by scales inherited from a number of validated and highly reliable studies, with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients exceeding the threshold of 0.7, which according to research by Hair et al (2013) is very good, highly reliable, ensuring eligibility for use in subsequent analyses. Measurement values such as Cronbach's alpha coefficient, composite reliability CR, convergence AVE, and discrimination all ensure the measurement conditions according to the above standards as researched by (Hair et al 2013). In addition, the Outer loading quality measurement index is > 0.708 ($\sqrt{0.5}$), so all scales ensure reliability and validity. The results show that the scales all achieve a high level of internal consistency, with Cronbach's Alpha coefficients exceeding the minimum threshold, confirming the homogeneity of the observed variables to the corresponding theoretical concepts, and confirming that the scales have high stability and consistency.

The EFA results show that the observed variables of the scale have a KMO index = 0.903 > 0.5, showing a strong enough correlation between the variables to conduct factor analysis. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity has $df = 6$, $Sig. = 0.001 < 0.05$, which is statistically significant, proving that the observed variables have a linear correlation with each other in the whole (Hair et al 2013). The variables converge into a single factor with an eigenvalue of 1.25, explaining 76.15% of the variance, and the factor loading coefficients are all above 0.5, showing that the scale is unidimensional and has a high convergent value.

Theoretical model testing analysis

After completing the assessment of the reliability and validity of the scale, the SEM linear structural model was used to measure the impact of MOC on BP at Vietnamese cashew enterprises. The SEM model was used because it is a multivariate analysis method, a powerful statistical tool to investigate complex relationships, providing a unified framework that includes many statistical procedures, can contain one or more dependent variables (endogenous), which helps to measure indirect relationships that multiple regression models cannot perform (Hair et al 2013).

Figure 2: SEM model hypothesis testing results (Source: author's analysis)

Based on the results of Figure 2, the coefficient of determination R^2 of KQ = 0.473, which means that the variables included in the model explain 47.3% of the change in the BP variable, with $p < 0.05$, which is statistically significant. In addition, the results of measuring the impact level of each factor in the model are described in detail in the table below, specifically:

Table 2: Estimation and hypothesis testing results

Hypothesis	Relationship	Impact coefficient β			t critical	P	VIF	Result
		Direct	Indirect	Total				
H1	MOC -> MFA	0.264		0.264	6.800	0.00	1.00	accept
H2	MOC -> CAD	0.270	0.084	0.313	6.230	0.00	1.07	accept
H3	MOC -> MCA	0.107	0.094	0.202	2.335	0.02	1.11	accept
H4	MOC -> CA	0.299	0.077	0.377	7.482	0.00	1.04	accept
H5	MFA -> CAD	0.163		0.163	3.777	0.00	1.07	accept
H6	CAD -> MCA	0.301		0.301	7.070	0.00	1.11	accept
H7	MCA -> CA	0.383		0.383	10.344	0.00	1.04	accept
H8	MFA -> BP	0.118	0.056	0.174	3.092	0.00	1.21	accept
H9	CAD -> BP	0.236	0.108	0.344	6.085	0.00	1.25	accept
H10	MCA -> BP	0.274	0.084	0.359	6.617	0.00	1.34	accept
H11	CA -> BP	0.220		0.220	5.277	0.00	1.48	accept
H12	MOC -> BP	0.150	0.243	0.393	4.463	0.00	1.24	accept

(Source: author's analysis)

All 12 hypotheses were accepted, the direct and indirect test results all gave positive impact indexes proving the influence from MOC to MFA, CAD, MCA, CA and BP, as well as the impact of MOC on CAD or from CAD to MCA, MCA to CA and from MFA, CAD, MCA, CA to BP. In which, MOC has a direct impact on BP with an impact coefficient of 0.150 and indirectly on BP through 4 variables MFA, CAD, MCA and CA with β reaching 0.243, the total impact index from MOC including indirect and direct on BP reaches 0.393, the highest among the hypotheses, meaning that when MOC increases by 1 standard deviation, BP increases by 0.393 standard deviations, or in other words, under the condition that other factors remain unchanged, when MOC increases by 1 unit, BP will increase by 0.393 units, this is a positive relationship with a fairly strong impact (Cohen, 2013).

The impact coefficients from MOC to CAD, CA, respectively, reached 0.313 and 0.377 or from CAD to MCA, BP, with β indexes reaching 0.301 and 0.344. Similarly, from MCA to CA, BP reached 0.383 and 0.359; these indexes all gave a strong positive impact. The remaining relationships, although giving lower indexes, are all positive, demonstrating the strong relationship of MOC through intermediaries. Specifically, the MOC variable has an impact on MFA with an index of β 0.264; MOC to MCA reaches 0.202; CA to BP reaches 0.220; the lowest are the MFA to CAD indexes reaching 0.163 and MFA to BP reaching 0.174. In addition, the results of measuring multicollinearity through the VIF coefficient show the VIF values of all independent variables in the models (Daoud, 2017).

The model explains 47.3% of the variation in business performance, the remaining variance of over 50% may stem from various factors not observed in the model. Firstly, macroeconomic factors such as export subsidy policies, tariff changes, technical barriers, and trade agreements can significantly impact business results. Secondly, fluctuations in input material prices and grain prices on the world market, as well as exchange rate fluctuations and international logistics costs, can distort the relationship between internal capacity and performance.

Furthermore, although the model has controlled for key mediating capabilities, the direct impact of MOC on BP may still exist. This shows that MOC not only affects BP through the development of specific capabilities, but also directly impacts business results through the quality of responses to customers, competitors, the environment, etc., thereby creating a direct impact on BP, going beyond the mediating role of functional capabilities.

Testing the model's fit to general data

Table 3: Model robustness testing

Impact	B research data	B 500 datas	SE	Bias	t critical
MOC -> MFA	0.264	0.261	0.002	0.003	1.68
MOC -> CAD	0.270	0.271	0.002	-0.001	0.52
MOC -> MCA	0.107	0.110	0.002	-0.003	1.56
MOC -> CA	0.299	0.299	0.002	0.000	0.00
MOC -> CAD	0.163	0.162	0.002	0.001	0.52
CAD -> MCA	0.301	0.301	0.002	0.000	0.00
MCA -> CA	0.383	0.383	0.002	0.000	0.00
MFA -> BP	0.118	0.119	0.002	-0.001	0.62
CAD -> BP	0.236	0.234	0.002	0.002	1.07
MCA -> BP	0.274	0.276	0.002	-0.002	1.07
CA -> BP	0.220	0.220	0.002	0.000	0.00
MOC -> BP	0.150	0.149	0.002	0.001	0.64

(Source: author's analysis)

The comparison result of the regression results from the research sample and the average estimated results of 500 samples (Table 4) shows that the difference value (bias) is relatively small, at the same time the statistical value t (t critical) <1.96, so there is no statistically significant difference between the measurement results built on the sample and the average results of 500 samples, so the measurement model that the research built is stable and suitable for the whole (Hair et al 2013).

Multigroup analysis

Table 4: Multigroup analysis with Positions of Leaders and Managers

Relationships	Path Coefficients-diff	P value original 1-tailed	P value new
MOC -> MFA	-0.174	0.984	0.032
MOC -> CAD	0.071	0.224	0.447
MOC -> MCA	-0.065	0.985	0.470

MOC -> CA	0.165	0.019	0.039
MFA -> CAD	-0.042	0.674	0.651
CAD -> MCA	-0.013	0.565	0.869
MCA -> CA	-0.044	0.723	0.554
MFA -> BP	-0.132	0.965	0.071
CAD -> BP	0.066	0.200	0.401
MCA -> BP	0.018	0.415	0.830
CA -> BP	0.068	0.208	0.416
MOC -> BP	-0.085	0.892	0.216

(Source: author's analysis)

The results from Table 5 above show selective differences in the level of evaluation by leaders and managers regarding the relationships studied. Specifically, for the MOC → MFA ($p = 0.032$) and MOC → CA ($p = 0.039$), the evaluation levels between the two groups differed statistically significantly, reflecting differences in how these two levels of management perceive the role of MOC in predictability and CA. Conversely, in other relationships ($p > 0.05$), the evaluation levels of the two groups were relatively similar, indicating consistent perceptions between senior leadership and middle management.

Conclusion

Discussion and Conclusion

The research results show the direct and indirect impact of MOC on BP through 4 intermediate variables Market Forecasting Ability, Changing Adaptability, Market Creating Ability and Competitive Advantage, and also show the relationship between intermediate variables. MOC promotes learning from customers, competitors and the environment, creating a solid foundation to help businesses forecast the market, upcoming changes to prevent and have appropriate development strategies, thereby improving the ability to adapt to changes, creating internal strength to be able to move towards establishing the market and being proactive in a volatile environment, helping to improve competitive advantage and achieve high business performance.

The high average value of market forecasting ability indicates that cashew industry businesses focus on monitoring and predicting fluctuations in the international market. This result is consistent with the trade context presented in the introduction, where data from the Vinacas and the General Statistics Office show that the cashew industry is heavily dependent on exports and frequently faces risks related to price fluctuations, exchange rates, and market demand. Therefore, strengthening market forecasting can be seen as an adaptive response by businesses to mitigate risks and stabilize business performance.

Management implications

Based on the research results, the following management implications are presented for businesses, especially Vietnamese cashew businesses, regarding closely monitoring market fluctuations. This includes understanding customer needs, competitor actions, and changing consumer preferences, as well as closely tracking economic and political developments in various countries. Strengthening information and knowledge, maintaining a proactive position in all situations, and ultimately improving competitiveness and achieving desired business results are crucial.

Strengthening and developing MOC

The highest average values for variables MOC1 3.59 and MOC2 3.58 (Appendix 01) indicate the importance of closely monitoring changes in the business environment and customer needs. Next are variables MOC4 and MOC5 (3.44 and 3.49), emphasizing the importance of building and managing market share to create competitive advantage. Finally, variable MOC3 highly values collaboration between departments to respond promptly to changes in the business environment. Standard deviations less than 1 indicate low variability and relative consensus among the survey respondents.

Enhancing MFA

With mean values of all observed variables > 3 and standard deviations > 0.9 (Appendix 02), results confirm the importance of forecasting ability. To improve MFA, businesses need to quickly grasp changes in market prices, customer demand, and competitor reactions through the systematic collection, analysis, and interpretation of market information. When MOCs are strengthened on a foundation of accurate forecasting, businesses will increase their adaptability to the market, proactively adjusting product strategies, pricing, distribution channels, and market approaches to suit changing conditions, thereby improving operational efficiency and sustainably enhancing business results.

Enhancing market CAD

The mean values of all observed variables > 3 and standard deviations > 0.9 (Appendix 03) demonstrate the importance of CAD. To increase CAD, businesses need to quickly grasp and recognise market changes, from customer reactions to competitor actions or policy changes, and then promptly take appropriate action. Adaptability helps businesses minimise risks from market shocks, facilitates the timely exploitation of business opportunities, thereby improving operational efficiency and sustainably enhancing business results.

Enhancing MCA

The mean values of all observed variables are > 3 , and standard deviations are > 0.7 (Appendix 04), showing the importance of market establishment capability in increasing BP. MCA reflects a company's ability to proactively identify, form, and expand target market segments through building a customer network, distribution channels, and appropriate market access mechanisms. When businesses possess effective market setting capabilities, the systematic collection and use of market information contributes to enhancing their MOC.

Enhancing CA

The mean values of observed variables all > 3 and standard deviations > 0.7 (Appendix 05) show the importance of creating a unique CA in increasing BP. Businesses can build sustainable CA through differentiation, the ability to maintain long-term customer relationships, and the effective exploitation of market resources. The CA formed will be a key factor in driving operational efficiency and improving business results in the long term.

In summary, the research results confirm that MOC has a significant positive impact on BP. MOC, through a good understanding of customer needs and competitor reactions, and by closely monitoring policy changes, helps create MFA, thereby enabling easy adaptation and market establishment aligned with operational strengths, creating a unique competitive advantage and increasing business efficiency.

In terms of macro management, government needs to (1) Create online communication groups for businesses in the same industry to help businesses promptly grasp information and fluctuations that may affect industry operations. (2) Establish consulting associations, exchange information directly with businesses, help grasp information and difficulties of businesses to provide timely support; (3) Invest in improving network security software and modern information systems to create a secure foundation for businesses to quickly update information and develop safely; (4) Support the construction of a digital traceability system for raw cashew nuts imported from West Africa, helping businesses control origin, procurement conditions and effectively comply with the increasingly stringent standards of the US and EU markets.

Limitations and future research directions

Although the research achieved practical results, there are still limitations such as the scope of the research is only in the cashew industry, future research needs to expand to other industries to have a more comprehensive view. The study has not yet considered the impact and regulation factors from the internal environment of the enterprise such as culture, capital sources or external factors such as policy changes, the impact from competitors in the same industry or partners in other industries but still have the ability to influence such as suppliers, logistics... Further research needs to consider these factors as regulating variables that can impact business results as well as consider more intermediary factors to make the research model more comprehensive and accurate.

Declarations

AI Use Statement: The authors confirm that no Artificial Intelligence tools were used in the writing or production of this manuscript.

Data Availability Statement: The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author, Vo Thi Thuy Duong upon reasonable request.

Funding Statement: This research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors

Conflict of Interest: The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Ethical Approval: The study was conducted in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki. Informed consent was obtained from all individual respondents prior to data collection, and all survey data were strictly anonymised to ensure participant confidentiality.

Authors' Contributions: D.L.K.O conceived and designed the study; V.T.T.D performed the data collection; V.T.T.D analysed the data; V.T.T.D wrote the paper. All authors have read and agreed to the published version. - All authors have read and agreed to the published version.

Reference

- Ahmad, N. H., Seet, , & Pi-Shen. (2009). Understanding business success through the lens of SME founder-owners in Australia and Malaysia. *International Journal of Entrepreneurial Venturing*, 1(1), 72-87.
- Baker, W. E., & Sinkula, J. M. (1999). Learning orientation, market orientation, and innovation: Integrating and extending models of organizational performance. *Journal of Market-Focused Management*, 4(4), 295-308.
- Barney, J. (1991). Firm Resources and Sustained Competitive Advantage. *Journal of Management*.
- Cohen, J. (2013). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioural sciences: Routledge*.
- Daoud, J. I. (2017). *Multicollinearity and regression analysis*. Paper presented at the Journal of Physics: Conference Series.
- Day, G. S. (2011). Closing the marketing capabilities gap. *Journal of marketing*, 75(4), 183-195.
- Hair, J. F. và cộng sự. (2013). Partial least squares structural equation modeling: Rigorous applications, better results and higher acceptance. *Long range planning*, 46(1-2), 1-12.
- Hanaysha, J. R., & Al-Shaikh, M. E. (2024). Impact of entrepreneurial orientation, marketing capability, and market orientation on business sustainability and corporate reputation. *Discover Sustainability*, 5(1), 273.
- Irfandi, N. và cộng sự. (2025). The impact of market orientation, product innovation, and competitive advantage on the marketing performance of culinary enterprises: Empirical study in Kampar Regency, Indonesia. *Golden Ratio of Marketing and Applied Psychology of Business*, 5(1), 79-94.
- Jaworski, B. và cộng sự. (2000). Market-driven versus driving markets. *Journal of the Academy of Marketing Science*, 28(1), 45-54.
- Kaplan, R., & Norton, D. P. (1996). *The Balanced Scorecard*-. In: Harvard Business School Press.
- Lambin, J.-J., & Schuiling, I. (2012). *Market-driven management: Strategic and operational marketing*: Bloomsbury Publishing.
- Luo, T. và cộng sự. (2025). A study of the impact of corporate market forecasting capability on the accuracy of strategic decision-making based on computational analysis of business data.
- Martin, J. H. và cộng sự. (2009). Implementing a market orientation in small manufacturing firms: from cognitive model to action. *Journal of Small Business Management*, 47(1), 92-115.

Morgan, N. A. và cộng sự. (2009). Market orientation, marketing capabilities, and firm performance. *Strategic Management Journal*, 30(8), 909-920.

Narver, J. C., & Slater, S. F. (1990). The effect of a market orientation on business profitability. *Journal of Marketing*, 54(4), 20-35.

Nenonen, S., & Storbacka, K. (2021). Market-shaping: navigating multiple theoretical perspectives. *AMS review*, 11(3), 336-353.

Uhl-Bien, M., & Arena, M. (2018). Leadership for organizational adaptability: A theoretical synthesis and integrative framework. *The Leadership Quarterly*, 29(1), 89-104.

Wenzel, M. (2021). Transcending adaptation: Toward an examination of market-shaping capabilities as a sub-capability of organizational agility. *Journal of Competences, Strategy & Management*, 11, 1-12.

APPENDIX

APPENDIX 01

Table 5: Mean and Std. Deviation of variables for MOC

Variables	Source	Developing observed variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
MOC1	(Jaworski et al 2000; Narver and Slater, 1990)	Our company closely monitors changing environmental trends	3.59	0.888
MOC2		Our company closely monitors customer needs	3.58	0.947
MOC3		Our company has a unified team of departments to respond promptly to changes in the business environment	3.36	0.890
MOC4		Our company is able to build and manage market share effectively by closely monitoring the business environment	3.44	0.884
MOC5		Our company is progressively building a sustainable competitive advantage by gathering information from customers, competitors, and the business environment	3.49	0.793

(Source: inheriting, developing, and author's analysis)

APPENDIX 02

Table 6: Mean and Std. Deviation values of variables for the MFA

Variables	Source	Developing observed variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
MFA1	(Day, 2011)	Our company quickly adapts to changes in market prices	3.59	0.793
MFA2		Our company quickly adapts to reactions from competitors	3.58	0.787
MFA3		Our company quickly understands customer needs	3.60	0.821

(Source: inheriting, developing, and author's analysis)

APPENDIX 03

Table 7: Mean and Std. Deviation values of variables for CAD

Variables	Source	Developing observed variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
CAD1	Uhl-Bien and Arena (2018) -	The company's leadership is always quick to recognize changing signals from the market	3.47	0.954
CAD2		The company's leadership always responds quickly and effectively to market changes	3.53	0.922
CAD3		Quick responses to market changes or government policies help companies ensure a stable working environment and sustainable growth	3.53	0.971

(Source: inheriting, developing, and author's analysis)

APPENDIX 04

Table 8: Mean and Std. Deviation values of variables for the MCA

Variables	Source	Developing observed variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
MCA1	Wenzel (2021)	The company can leverage its available resources and ability to adapt quickly to changes in order to build its brand and expand its market.	3.64	0.796
MCA2		The company has consistently maintained its reputation amidst market changes, thereby building a reliable and loyal customer base	3.52	0.775
MCA3		The company can quickly adjust its business strategy to ensure it maintains its market share in the face of constantly	3.53	0.782

Variables	Source	Developing observed variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
		changing and unpredictable business environments		

(Source: inheriting, developing, and author's analysis)

APPENDIX 05

Table 9: Mean and Std. Deviation values of variables for the CA

Variables	Source	Developing observed variables	Mean	Std. Deviation
CA1	Barney (1991)	Our market adaptability resources help create customer satisfaction	3.41	0.906
CA2		The ability to withstand change creates unique value for our company	3.29	0.963
CA3		Our ability to observe and predict market trends helps us build a competitive advantage in business	3.13	0.990

(Source: inheriting, developing, and author's analysis)